

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING PHYSIOLOGY

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Abstract. *The article discusses the fact that an important task of a teacher is to form the right and constant motivation for studying this subject, noting the importance of extracurricular activities, study of science circles as the main component of the formation of professional competencies. Students are offered to solve situational problems that are as close as possible to the most common clinical situations encountered in the practical activities of future specialists.*

Keywords: *physiology teacher, biological education, biological education, training, research work.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ФИЗИОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. *В статье упоминается, что важной задачей учителя является формирование правильной и постоянной мотивации к изучению предмета, а также отмечается важность обучения во внеклассной деятельности и научных кружках как основной составляющей формирования профессиональных компетенций. Студентам предлагается решать ситуационные задачи, максимально приближенные к наиболее распространённым клиническим ситуациям в практической работе будущих специалистов.*

Ключевые слова: *учитель физиологии, биологическое образование, подготовка, исследование.*

Anatomy is one of the main subjects, and the knowledge gained as a result of studying it is used by students both in subsequent courses of study and in their future profession, therefore, the presentation of the material should be in a convenient form and the assimilation of the material should be at a high level. It is very important that the knowledge acquired by students is constantly updated and improved. The modern educational process is aimed at developing the ability to think creatively, logically, analyze, and compare, which ultimately leads to the formation of professional competencies. Based on anatomical knowledge, specialists make decisions on diagnosis, provide assistance, and conduct treatment.

The effectiveness of the educational material largely depends on the self-management of students. In the process of self-control, special attention is paid not only to the student's ability to answer ready-made questions, but also to the ability to formulate them independently. A positive attitude to studying the subject is created through a rating system for assessing students' academic work. This system allows you to identify the best students and encourages them to study the educational material in depth. The participation of students in the ongoing Olympiads has a stimulating effect on the level of assimilation and retention of the material. Becoming a winner of the Olympiad is always prestigious for a student! Materials for the Olympiad are compiled by experienced teachers taking into account clinical situations. An important lever for the development of professional competencies of students is participation in educational and research work. Educational and research work helps to update the knowledge gained and solve complex issues with the teacher. Practice shows that the topics that students have completed during educational and research work have the deepest level of assimilation.

An anatomy and physiology teacher is a highly qualified specialist who plays a key role in medical and biological education. His main task is to convey knowledge about the structure and functions of the human body, as well as its systems and organs. This knowledge serves as the basis for future doctors, nurses and other health care professionals.

His/her duties include developing curricula, creating teaching materials, conducting lectures, seminars, and practical sessions. The teacher must be aware of current research and trends in the field of anatomy and physiology, ensuring that teaching is relevant. He/she also develops critical thinking by teaching students to analyze and interpret data.

Deep study of the complex processes occurring in the human body

This knowledge is important not only for students of medical and biological sciences, but also for a wider audience, opening up opportunities for interdisciplinary cooperation.

Formation of critical thinking and analytical skills

During the training, students learn not only to memorize information, but also to apply it in practice, which is especially important for future doctors and medical workers. This allows them to solve problems in real clinical situations more effectively.

The opportunity to constantly develop and learn new things

Scientific discoveries and achievements in the field of medicine occur at a rapid pace, so teachers can always be aware of modern trends and pass on their knowledge to new generations.

This makes the profession dynamic and interesting, filling it with meaning and significance.

Widespread use of the wide interdisciplinary connections between anatomy and physiology and other disciplines is one of the ways to improve the quality of teaching in this subject.

Given the complexity and volume of the program material on the topic (the content of the training material includes a huge number of didactic units), the teacher should not forget about the need to develop motivation in students to study this subject.

If we consider the mass of anatomical facts in its pure form, that is, isolated from other subjects, then the student does not have a clear and meaningful idea of why this mass of facts should be studied, where this information will be needed in the future. In other words, there is no significant motivation to study anatomy, and conscientiously memorized knowledge is quickly forgotten.

However, in order to form an interest in studying the subject in students, an enthusiastic approach, it is absolutely not enough to limit oneself to a general instruction in the introductory lecture on the role of anatomy, physiology and pathology in the study of medical science.

For each section of the program, the student must be convinced that specific anatomical and physiological information is needed in the study of specific clinical subjects. Only this approach creates a clear motivation in students to memorize this information.

For the teacher, this means the need to study each section of the program in detail from the point of view of determining the interdisciplinary relevance of the subject. The teacher must clearly understand what anatomical information is clinically significant, that is, will definitely be in demand in the future by training clinicians. There are several ways to separate this information from the whole mass of anatomical facts. Direct discussion of each section of the program with teachers of clinical sciences, systematic participation in clinician training, study of the content of textbooks on clinical sciences, study of work programs and calendar-thematic plans - all this is effective.

Having completed this work, the teacher will be able to show with specific examples how knowledge of anatomy and physiology is applied in medical practice. Such examples can be given in each section of the program. In addition, students should be drawn to the anatomical and physiological features of organs, which, if such features are found, can be important in the development of pathology.

Such an approach to teaching, undoubtedly, increases motivation to study the subject. The knowledge presented in this way is perceived with great interest and is stored in memory longer.

In conclusion, when studying anatomical terms, you should take into account that many of them will not be used by the student in the future. At the same time, many of them have Greek synonyms, from which many clinical terms are formed. Therefore, special attention should be paid to these Greek-Latin names. Already in the process of studying anatomy, students can get acquainted with the vast world of clinical terminology, which increases students' interest in science and medicine. Such an approach to teaching the subject leads to an increase in the quality of personnel training, and anatomy becomes a real medical passport for students.

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